

FLEXURAL PERFORMANCE AND PROCESS CONDITIONS OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE LAMINATES PROCESSED BY AUTOMATED TAPE PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has high specific stiffness/strength as well as excellent corrosion resistance in comparison with metallic alloys such as steel and aluminum alloy. CFRP with high strength is typically processed by using thermoset prepregs and an autoclave. This processing method is expensive, slow, labor-intensive, and limited in size. Also, recycling and shelf life of thermoset prepregs have limitations. Therefore, the development of inexpensive and out-of-autoclave processing technology for CFRP is a significant key factor to boost the availability of CFRP while maintaining adequate strength.

Herein, we investigate the feasibility and advantages of in-situ consolidated carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) laminates. The emphasis is placed on experimentally evaluating flexural performance of the in-situ consolidated laminates as compared with baseline specimens made through a hot press process. An automated tape placement (ATP) machine manufactured by Automated Dynamics is adopted for this study, and this machine includes a unidirectional prepreg tape, compaction roller, heat source device, and computer numerical control. Experimental work is conducted to understand the interaction of materials characterization with voids and temperatures. In parallel, computational simulations are undertaken on commercial finite element software, ABAQUS, to understand the mechanical-thermal response of a laminated plate; specifically, displacements, stresses, and temperatures. The results showed that flexural strength of CFRTP processed by in situ ATP corresponded to 38% - 49% of the strength of the baseline. Also, the computational result highlighted that the compaction force of 539 N led to through-thickness stresses in a range of 35 MPa and 64 MPa propagated in the laminate. This study will be extended to address the relationship between microstructure and strength for finding the optimal process conditions of CFRTP.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) providing high specific strength/stiffness has been primarily used for aerospace structures such as tail wings, main wings, and fuselage of a commercial airplane. The current technique to manufacture the large curved skin panels of an aircraft is a 2-step

process, automated tape laying and consolidation in autoclave. An automated tape placement (ATP) process with a laser heating system is employed, and CF/thermoset composite laminates with either copper or aluminum metallization are processed in ATP and successfully consolidated in autoclave [1]. The processing method is expensive, slow, labor-intensive, and limited in size. Also, recycling and shelf life of thermoset prepregs have limitations. Therefore, the development of inexpensive and out-of-autoclave processing technology for CFRP is a significant key factor to boost the availability of CFRP in the automobile and wind energy industries while maintaining adequate specific strength and excellent price-performance ratio.

Three manufacturing methods to make laminates with high mechanical performance during ATP process are considered: complete in situ consolidation, partial consolidation followed by an out-of-autoclave process, and partial consolidation followed by autoclave consolidation. The thermoplastic ATP built by Automated Dynamics, one of the pioneers in the in situ ATP field, is suited to particularly cylindrical structures and allows their fabrication of high quality up to 7 inches thick. Since a tape is consolidated for a fraction of a second, a tape may loft or rebound causing void inclusion and fiber waviness. Lofting and rebounding degrade the mechanical properties of flat parts [2]. The process parameters (compaction force, tape laying speed, and tool temperature) of the in situ consolidation of CF/PEEK prepreg tape during ATP were experimentally investigated to find the potential and possibilities of this technology by evaluating the interlaminar shear strength, single lap shear strength, and fracture toughness. A hot gas nozzle that was wider than a tape provided a much better heat distribution along a compaction roller. The specimens manufactured by ATP with a hot-gas torch only achieved 55% of the interlaminar shear strength obtained from autoclaved baseline specimens [3]. The deformation behavior of CF/PEEK prepregs caused by a compaction roller and the tape/substrate orientation during ATP was investigated to improve laminate integrity [4].

The influence of three different heating systems (flame, hot gas, and infrared) on wedge peel strength of CF/PEEK layers manufactured during in-situ consolidation of ATP was examined along with consolidation force, tape laying speed, and gas flow rate. The maximum values of both the wedge peel resistance and bending strength occurred in the same range of gas flow rate. Due to engineering and economic reasons, the hot gas heating system proved to be the most efficient method [5]. Additionally, laser heating technology to deliver heat source to a tape was developed recently and contributed to the increase of fracture toughness since temperature in the nip region was controlled precisely [6]. Accudyne patented thermoplastic ATP heads developed for heat transfer, reptation/healing, crystalline melting, crystallinity generation, and avoiding degradation. The ATP head could process laminates to achieve 89% - 97% of various strengths measured from autoclaved laminates [7].

2D and 3D finite element (FE) modeling were undertaken to predict the final slit tape thickness and the single tape/tape gap width during ATP. The results of 2D FE analysis agreed well with those of 3D FE analysis only when the prepregs were stiff enough and no lateral tape/tape contact occurred [8]. It was demonstrated that the through-thickness compressive behavior of uncured CF/epoxy prepregs employed during ATP could be modelled as orthotropic elasto-plastic materials with strain hardening instead of using visco-elastic response of the uncured prepregs [9]. In-plane and out-of-plane shear deformation characteristics of single and multiple stacks of unidirectional (UD) prepregs were studied to demonstrate that a simple tensile specimen where fibers oriented at 15° could provide sufficient information on the shear behavior of UD prepreg [10]. While ATP technologies mentioned above have been studied at various universities, companies, and institutes in the US and Europe, in situ consolidation of ATP has been studied in Japan as well to achieve economical, fast-cycle, and robust carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP), which can be used for various applications such as automotive, aviation, marine, and wind energy [11,12].

Herein, we investigate the feasibility and advantages of in situ consolidated CFRTP laminates. The emphasis is placed on experimentally evaluating flexural performance of in situ consolidated laminates as compared with baseline specimens made through a hot press process. Experimental work is conducted to understand the interaction of materials characterization with voids and temperatures. In parallel, computational simulations are undertaken on commercial finite element software, ABAQUS, to understand the mechanical-thermal response of a laminated plate; specifically, displacements, stresses, and temperatures.

2 IN SITU AUTOMATED TAPA PALACEMENT

An ATP machine manufactured by Automated Dynamics is adopted for this study as presented in Figure 1(a). This machine includes a UD prepreg slit tape, compaction roller, heat source device, and computer numerical control. A slit tape is heated and is delivered to a compaction roller by which a compaction force acts on the tape. This machine enables to array a slit tape arbitrary and automatically. A thermoplastic prepreg slit tape (sourced by PMC Baycomp, currently becoming a part of TenCate) used for this study is carbon fiber-reinforced polyamide 6 (CF/PA6). The fiber content in the tape is 62% by weight; the width and thickness of a slit tape are 12.78 mm (0.5 inches) and 0.22 mm, respectively. As shown in Figure 1(b), nitrogen gas at high temperature delivered through a gas torch heats a slit tape around a nip point. The tape is consolidated by a compaction roller and is stacked on a tool. Note that the temperature of nitrogen gas measured at the tip of the torch can be controlled. It was confirmed that the temperature of the gas staying below the roller ranged from 250 °C to 300 °C, which was above the melting point of the PA6 resin when the temperature of the nitrogen gas was set to 500 °C on the control panel of the ATP machine. The interesting process parameters for this study are compaction force, tape laying speed, gas flow rate, and temperature at gas torch.

Figure 1: (a) Automated tape placement machine, and (b) schematic of in situ consolidation process.

3 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

3.1 Bending specimen preparation

The process variables for bending specimens and their corresponding names are summarized in Table 1 where $l-55$, $f-80$, and $v-75$ are the identical condition. The laminated strips were processed in the ATP machine at the temperature of 500 °C. In the strips, the prepreg tape was stacked in 10 plies along the 0° direction on the tool. Two specimens were obtained from each 10-ply strip by using a diamond cutter, and the first and second specimens corresponded to 100 mm - 200 mm and 200 mm - 300 mm of a strip, respectively, as seen in Figure 2. The specimens were 100 mm long, 15 mm - 18 mm wide, and 1.8 mm - 2.4 mm thick. The varying widths and thicknesses of the specimens arose from different process conditions. In the prepreg tape heated by hot gas, the fluidity of the resin improved, and the tape was allowed to spread in the normal direction to the fiber direction while the roller compressed the tape. Due to polymer with high water absorbability, all specimens were dried in a vacuum oven at 80 °C for 16 hours. At least four specimens for each process condition were prepared for the test. In parallel, specimens were manufactured through hot pressing by using CF/PA6 prepreg tape.

A tape heated by hot gas initially expanded due to the thermal characteristics of a resin. Since tool, ambient air, and substrate gradually deprived the incoming tape of heat, residual strains between plies occurred after completing processing (i.e., cooling down). The curved 10-ply strips were manufactured as presented in Figure 2. The radii of curvature of strips were measured to estimate the residual strain

and stress in the strips. An expression for the residual strain developed by Bailey *et al.* [13] is employed to calculate the residual stress, and it can be simplified to Equation (1) where ε_r is the residual strain; t , a thickness of a strip; r , radius of curvature of a strip. The residual stress can be found in Equation (2) where σ_r is a residual stress in a strip; E_1 , the elastic modulus in the 1-direction.

$$\varepsilon_r = 2t/3r \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_r = E_1 \varepsilon_r \quad (2)$$

Table 1: Process conditions.

Label of the condition	Compaction force [N] ([kgf])	Gas flow rate [l/min]	Tape laying velocity [mm/sec]
<i>l-50</i>	490 (50)	80	75
<i>l-55</i>	539 (55)	80	75
<i>l-60</i>	588 (60)	80	75
<i>l-65</i>	637 (65)	80	75
<i>f-60</i>	539 (55)	60	75
<i>f-70</i>	539 (55)	70	75
<i>f-80</i>	539 (55)	80	75
<i>f-90</i>	539 (55)	90	75
<i>v-55</i>	539 (55)	80	55
<i>v-65</i>	539 (55)	80	65
<i>v-75</i>	539 (55)	80	75
<i>v-85</i>	539 (55)	80	85

Figure 2: Warp of a 10-ply strip having the radius of curvature of 1880 mm.

3.2 Mechanical Testing

JIS K 7074:1988 guidance is used to prepare and test CFRP specimens to estimate the maximum flexural strength and flexural modulus [14]. The schematic of three point bending test is presented in Figure 3 where the specimen is placed on two supporting pins; their distance is 80 mm; the loading pin applies a force in the exact middle of the two supports.

Figure 3: Schematic of three point bending test.

To accomplish this test, we are going to use the two following equations:

$$E_b = \frac{1}{4} \frac{L^3}{bt^3} \frac{P}{\delta} \quad (3)$$

where E_b is flexural modulus; P , a load; δ , deflection corresponding to P ; L , the distance between two supporting pins; b , the width of a specimen; t , the thickness of a specimen.

$$\sigma_b = \frac{3P_b L}{2bt^2} \quad (4)$$

where σ_b is the maximum bending stress; P_b , a fracture load.

3.3 Bending test procedure

A universal testing machine (Autograph AG-500B, Shimadzu) was used to load the specimens. The integrated materials testing software (TRAPEZIUM, Shimadzu) was used for data collection during the test. The crosshead displacement was controlled at a rate of 5 ± 1 mm/min. All specimens were in a dry state. The specimen was loaded until it failed (i.e., significant drop in a loading - displacement curve was observed).

3.4 Bending test results

The flexural moduli and the maximum bending stresses of the specimens were obtained from bending tests. The curvatures of the specimens were measured and distributed between 1,600 mm and 2,900 mm. Then, the residual stresses in the specimens were estimated in Equations (1), (2). The flexure moduli and their corresponding confidence interval (CI) are presented in Table 2, and the maximum bending stresses and residual stresses in the specimens for each process parameter are summarized in Figures 4-6. Since the shape of the specimens was an upward-convex curve, their maximum bending stress obtained from bending test was overestimated. Thus, the actual flexural strength of the specimen could be equivalent to the difference between the maximum bending stress and residual stress. From the test, the baseline specimen experienced the flexural modulus of 86.9 GPa and the maximum bending stress of 1260 MPa while the literature values for the flexural modulus and flexural strength of the UD prepreg tape (Cetex TC960 Nylon 6, TenCate) were 97 GPa and 950 MPa, respectively [15]. Therefore, the reliability of the testing technique and bending results were confirmed. The concave downward

The relationship between compaction force and stress of the specimen was presented in Figure 4. It was seen in Figure 4 that the residual stress (up to 54.2 MPa) of a specimen manufactured under a process condition was much below its corresponding maximum bending stress. There was the greatest value of 11.1% for the residual stress ratio defined as the residual stress of a specimen manufactured under a process condition over its corresponding maximum bending stress. From Table 2, the flexural

modulus of a specimen varied, depending on the magnitude of the compaction force. The similar trend in the change of the maximum bending stress was observed in Figure 4. In addition, there was no relationship between bonding capacity and compaction force though it was simply believed to increase bonding capacity between layers as an increasing compaction force.

As shown in Figure 5, the maximum stress significantly increased to 616 MPa when nitrogen gas flow rate increased from 60 l/min to 70 l/min. Since the heated portion of the tape was extensively exposed due to increasing the flow rate, the resin of the tape was uniformly melted, and the melting and solidification conditions between the layers were improved. The maximum stress of the specimens (*f-70, f-80, f-90*) located in the range of 520 MPa to 620 MPa with a narrow CI. The range matched 41 % - 49 % of the normalized flexural strength that was defined as the maximum bending stress of a specimen over the flexural strength of the baseline specimen. Thus, this indicated that the flow rate of 70 l/min was sufficient to provide adequate flexural strength. The *f-60* specimen experienced the greatest residual stress of 76.4 MPa, corresponding to 26.2% of its maximum stress while the other specimens (*f-70, f-80, f-90*) contained 10% of the residual stress ratio. At the flow rate of 100 l/min, the tape was often tearing in the fiber direction, and it was not possible to successfully fuse incoming tape on the substrate.

It was seen in Figure 6 that maximum stress reached at the greatest value of 703 MPa (56 % of the normalized flexural strength) at the tape laying velocity of 55 mm/sec. The residual stress ratio varied from 4.2% to 10.3%. When the process parameters except the tape laying velocity were constrained, it was expected the maximum value for flexural strength occurred at the velocity of 0 mm/sec (i.e., static states). It was reasonable that the maximum stress increased as decreasing the velocity (i.e., this result approached a static result). Since in situ consolidation of ATP technology is expected to be high cycle speed process, it is required that calibrating process parameters except the tape laying velocity achieves sufficient interlaminar bond strength at a faster process rate.

In order to accomplish in situ consolidation of ATP technology, it is necessary to improve the flexural strength as well as to avoid the occurrence of curved laminates. To overcome this issue, we will heat the forming tool at a constant temperature which is above glass transition temperature during ATP by an infrared heater. Since the material for the baseline specimen was not identical to one used in the ATP machine, the results of the specimens processed by in situ ATP will be compared with the results of the specimens made by hot press technology with using the prepreg tape used in this study.

Table 2: Flexural moduli of specimens.

Process condition	Flexural modulus [GPa]	95% CI [GPa]
<i>l-50</i>	72.8	4.8
<i>l-55</i>	64.5	4.2
<i>l-60</i>	59.5	2.5
<i>l-65</i>	65.4	8.6
<i>f-60</i>	73.4	25.0
<i>f-70</i>	76.6	5.1
<i>f-80</i>	64.5	4.2
<i>f-90</i>	66.9	4.4
<i>v-55</i>	72.6	0.8
<i>v-65</i>	56.3	1.7
<i>v-75</i>	64.5	4.2
<i>v-85</i>	69.5	10.7

Figure 4: Maximum bending and residual stress vs. compaction force.

Figure 5: Maximum bending and residual stress vs. gas flow rate.

Figure 6: Maximum bending and residual stress vs. tape laying velocity.

4 COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH

The information on mechanical behavior, thermal behavior, melting, and solidification of a prepreg tape cannot be easily captured throughout experimental work. Computational analysis was adopted to understand the stress state and deformed shape of a prepreg tape during in situ ATP and was performed on commercial finite element software, Abaqus/Standard.

4.1 Geometries/FE models

The schematic of the model used in the simulation is presented in Figure 7. The uncured CF/PA6 prepreg slit tape had a width of 12.7 mm, a length of 30 mm, and a thickness of 0.16 mm while the metallic compaction roller had a diameter of 12.7 mm and a width of 13.7 mm. A slit tape was laminated layer by layer to be a 4-ply strip with 0.64 mm in thickness. For simplicity, the change in the dimensions generated by ATP process was ignored in the simulation. Since it was very difficult to model bonding between an incoming tape (Ply-4) and substrate, it was assumed that Ply-4 and Ply-3 were perfectly bonded before applying a compaction force.

Figure 7: Schematic of the simulated model.

Due to symmetry of the roller and layer, the half FE model was created in Abaqus/CAE to reduce modeling and computational time. Thus, the layer was 6.35 mm wide, 30 mm long, and 0.64 mm thick. The layer was modeled with 3D solid (C3D8R) elements. The mesh size of 0.2 mm was employed, generating 19456 elements in the layer. C3D8R elements were 8-node linear brick, reduced integration with hourglass control [16]. On the other hand, the roller represented by an analytical rigid surface had a diameter of 12.7 mm and a width of 6.85 mm. Instead of using rigid body elements, analytical rigid surfaces were suitable for modeling many curved geometries exactly [16]. This contributed for reducing contact noise and providing a better approximation to the physical contact constraint. Thereby, the reduction in computational cost incurred by the contact algorithm was expected. Since an analytical rigid surface did not contribute to the mass and rotary inertia properties of the rigid body, its actual mass of 1.14945×10^{-2} kg was assigned as a point mass at the centroid of the roller.

4.2 Material model

Since the CF/PA6 prepreg was a thermoplastic material, specimens manufactured in a hot press machine were prepared for tensile tests to obtain their temperature-dependent mechanical properties as described in detail in [11]. The prepreg tape was treated as a homogenous material with transversely isotropic elastic properties though the test data was recorded until the specimens failed.

The temperature dependent elastic properties are summarized in Table 3. Since the fiber properties dominate the 1-direction of the UD prepreg tape, E_1 , ν_{12} , ν_{13} , G_{12} , and G_{13} of the prepreg are of

temperature independence. It is assumed that ν_{23} and G_{23} are not temperature dependent because of the lack of experimental technique and skills. Due to transversely isotropic properties, we have the following relationships: $E_2 = E_3$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$, and $G_{12} = G_{13}$. The prepreg is treated as an incompressive material, leading to $\nu_{23} = 0.5$ at any temperature.

Table 3: Elastic properties of the prepreg for the simulation.

E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	Temperature [°C]
99.1	7.23	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	20
99.1	6.11	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	30
99.1	4.25	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	50
99.1	2.37	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	70
99.1	2.11	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	90
99.1	1.70	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	110
99.1	0.856	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	130
99.1	0.0616	2.50	1.60	0.372	0.5	225

4.3 Analysis details

Quasi-static analysis with nonlinear geometries was performed during 0.38 sec through the dynamic implicit method on Abaqus/Standard. The event with the tape laying velocity of 75 mm/sec was treated in the simulation.

4.3.1 Interaction

Since the roller contacted with the layer, it was required to define their interactions. The contact pair algorithm with the finite-sliding tracking approach and frictionless contact was utilized to account for the relative motion of the interaction between the roller and the layer in the simulation. The finite-sliding contact allowed for arbitrary relative separation, sliding, and rotation of the contacting surfaces [16]. A rigid surface of the roller was assigned for the master surface of contact pair algorithm while the top face of the layer (i.e., the top face of Ply-4) was defined as its slave surface.

4.3.2 Boundary and loading conditions

The U_2 displacement of the roller increased linearly to 0.121 m by 0.3 sec and then remained to be a constant from 0.3 sec to 0.38 sec. This represented the application of a compaction force. The V_1 velocity of 75 mm/sec and ω_3 angular velocity of 11.81 rad/sec were instantaneously assigned at the centroid of the roller at the beginning of the analysis. The other degrees of freedom were fully constrained.

In the 4-ply layer, the Z symmetry condition (i.e., symmetry about a global plane Z, $U_3=UR_1=UR_2=0$) was applied for one surface seen in Figure 8. Note that there existed three displacement degrees of freedom in the solid elements. The bottom surface of the layer was fully constrained (i.e., $U_1=U_2=U_3=0$). The temperature distribution of the layer during in situ ATP was measured with Type T thermocouples and data logger (GL220, Graphtec) and was presented in Table 4 [11]. The 4-ply layer was divided into 4 regions denoted by L-1, L-2, L3, and L-4 as seen in Figure 7, and uniform temperature was assigned to each region.

Figure 8: Boundary and loading conditions.

Table 4: Temperature distribution in degree Celsius.

	L-1	L-2	L-3	L-4
Ply-4	280	280	280	280
Ply-3	77.4	80.1	83.8	87.2
Ply-2	68.8	69.4	67.5	73.5
Ply-1	40.3	40.7	41.1	41.4

4.4 The results of the analysis

The results of finite element analysis (FEA) are presented in Figure 9 where the S_{33} stress is measured in MPa and represents through-thickness stress of the 4-ply layer; displacement along the global Y-axis is plotted; the force along the Y-axis is equivalent to a compaction force. It was seen in Figure 9(a) that the displacement parabolically increased with an increasing the force. Since non recoverable deformation was not taken into account in the analysis, the layer went back to its original shape after a compaction force was released by moving the roller. The local deformation of the layer which the roller compressed was observed in Figure 9(b). The greatest S_{33} stress of 63.9 MPa was presented at the force of 539 N, which produced the displacement of 0.102 mm. The stress distribution that was similar to Figure 9(b) was observed at any given point in time since the elastic material was used in the simulation. The local deformation occurred in Ply-4 only while the other plies did not experienced severe deformations. At the force of 539 N, the S_{33} stress propagated to Ply-1 and decreased to 35 MPa located in Ply-1.

Figure 9: (a) Displacement vs force along the global Y-axis, (b) S_{33} stress in MPa at Force-1.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The bending test of specimens processed by in situ ATP was performed to evaluate the effect of process parameters (compaction force, gas flow rate, and tape laying velocity) on the flexural performance of the specimens. It was found from the results of bending tests that the gas flow rate made an impact on interlaminar bond strength rather than compaction force and tape laying velocity. The maximum bending stress of the consolidated specimens corresponded to 38% - 49% of the flexural strength of the baseline specimen. For practical applications of the in situ consolidation technology, it is necessary to improve interlayer bonding. Also, it is necessary to propose a method for suppressing the effects of thermal expansion and contraction of the tape to mold the flat plate since the consolidated specimens contained warping with a radius of curvature (1,600 mm - 2,900 mm). Furthermore, the result of the computational analysis highlighted that the compaction force of 539 N led to through-thickness stresses in a range of 35 MPa and 64 MPa propagated in the 4-ply layer. Further development of the computational model is needed to capture the non-recoverable deformation and bonding mechanism.

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